

SEARCHING FOR A SIGNATURE: A FILE FORMAT IDENTIFICATION WORKSHOP

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Abstract – File format identification is generally accepted as a key digital preservation activity as it enables preservation practitioners to understand, manage, and mitigate format-related risks and challenges.

This foundational workshop will explore the concepts and practical approaches to file format identification.

The workshop assumes no prior knowledge or experience of file format identification, and aims to cater to different learning styles with a selection of interactive activities.

Submission Type – Workshop.

Keywords – Identification, Format Assessment, Characterisation.

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey.

I. INTRODUCTION

iPRES has previously hosted file format identification workshops in 2018 [1], 2022 [2], and 2024 [3]. Feedback from the ‘Container Signature Workshop’ in 2024 was clear that participants would highly value a foundational-level workshop on the

concepts and practical approaches to file format identification.

As previous file format workshops have taken place in Europe and North America, iPRES 2025 is an opportunity to host this kind of workshop for a new audience.

This interactive workshop will suit any digital preservation practitioner interested in learning more about file format identification.

Participants do not need any prior experience in file format identification practices. Participants are encouraged to bring laptop computers, and it is recommended to have the following tools installed in advance of the workshop:

- DROID
- Seigfried
- HxD (or any similar hex editor tool)
- 7-Zip

By the end of the workshop participants will have an understanding of the technical mechanisms for file format identification, familiarity with common tools used for file format identification, an understanding of techniques for finding file format

examples, familiarity with techniques for creating file format signatures, and an understanding of how to submit updates and new submissions to PRONOM and other public file format resources.

Ideally this workshop will be delivered in-person in a room accommodating approximately 50 participants.

Ideally, this workshop will take place over three hours, split into two 90-minute sessions with a minimum 20-minute break in between.

II. TOPICS

Workshop topics will include:

1) *File format fundamentals*: What is a file format? Bits, bytes and data structures.

2) *File Format Identification Tools*: A hands-on introduction to DROID and Seigfried and a discussion of other file format identification tools.

3) *File Format technical resources*: An exploration of PRONOM, WikiData, Library of Congress Sustainability Resource, and the Just Solve It File Format Wiki.

4) *PRONOM-based file format identification*: An introduction to the PRONOM file format signature scheme.

5) *Finding format samples*: Techniques for finding file format examples to aid the creation of file format signatures.

6) *Submitting your findings*: Demonstrations of how to contribute to PRONOM and other file format resources.

7) *Advanced topics*: A brief overview of container signatures, Macintosh file identification, and any further file format topics workshop participants would like to explore.

Following the more advanced 2024 workshop, the authors wish to offer this foundational workshop with the aim of providing a more structured syllabus developed from the ground-up. This syllabus can be delivered more effectively by digital preservation colleagues, whether in person or remotely, to support communities with limited resources or those unable to attend iPRES at this time.

The authors intend to replicate surveys conducted before and after the 2024 workshop and

incorporate feedback into this syllabus through participatory design.

REFERENCES

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- [3] D. Clipsham, F. Mackenzie, R. Spencer, T. Thorsted, "What's in the Box? Container-based File Format Identification," in iPres 2024 Conference, Ghent, 2024

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

David Clipsham is the File Format Analyst at Preservica, supporting system users in overcoming their file format-related challenges. He previously worked at The National Archives (UK), where among many roles, he spear-headed PRONOM file format research for around 10 years.

Tyler Thorsted is the Digital Preservation Manager for Brigham Young University in Provo, Utah. He enjoys file format research and has been creating signatures for PRONOM since attending the file format workshop at iPres 2018 in Boston. He specializes in Macintosh based format identification.

Ross Spencer is a long-standing contributor to the digital preservation community, facilitating and enhancing processes for file format signature development through the creation of tools such as the PRONOM signature development utility and the skeleton test suite. He has written extensively on file format analysis for The National Archives, UK; Archives New Zealand, The Open Preservation Foundation; and on his own platforms.

Dr Sonia Ranade is Head of Digital Archiving at The National Archives (UK). She is interested in service automation, developing archival theory and practice for the digital age and in probabilistic approaches to describing, enriching and linking archival data.

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